

RNI UPBIL/2008/28046

ISSN No. : 0976-3406

शिक्षामित्र

वर्ष 3 अंक 4

जून 2011

Shikshamitra

अनुक्रमणिका

• हमारे धर्म ग्रन्थों में नारी	डॉ. राजकुमारी वर्मा	3
• कहाँ गए आदर्श शिक्षक	डॉ. योगेन्द्र योगीराज	4
• शिक्षा और जीवन मूल	डॉ. श्रीमती अरुणा भदौरिया	5
• बौद्धकालीन शिक्षा का प्रमुख केन्द्र : नालन्दा विश्व.	डॉ. (श्रीमती) रुचि मिश्रा	6
• नैतिक शिक्षा के प्रति शिक्षकों की अभिवृत्ति...	पायल शर्म	7
• विद्यालय शिक्षकों में मानसिक स्वास्थ्य का...	मीना पवार एवं उषा कुमावत	9
• वर्तमान परिदृश्य में अध्यापक शिक्षा की गुणवत्ता...	डॉ. रश्मि श्रीवास्तव	11
• विज्ञान, धर्म और विकास	अमित वर्मा "शान्तज"	13
• बच्चों को सीखने-सिखाने के प्रति हमारा दृष्टिकोण	डॉ. एस. सी. बहुगुणा	14
• मातृभाषा और शिक्षा	डॉ. सरोज गर्ग	16
• कबीर की साखियों में निहित शैक्षिक मूल्य	डॉ. शशि चित्तौड़ा एवं ललित कुमार श्रीमाली	17
• शिक्षा में नवाचार - आधुनिकता की ओर बढ़ते कदम	डॉ. मधुरिमा सिंह	19
• वंशानुक्रम तथा वातावरण की सापेक्षिक उपयोगिता	डॉ. अमित मित्तल	21
• मानव सम्बन्ध	डॉ. नरेश कुमार नेमा	22
• बहुकक्षा व बहुस्तरीय शिक्षण युक्तियाँ	डॉ. दिनेश कुमार	24
• नारी एक उभरती शक्ति	अनुपमा यादव	26
• भारत में बालिका शिक्षा : दशा एवं दिशा	संजीव शुक्ला	27
• वैश्वीकरण के परिदृश्य में दैनिक हिन्दी समाचार....	अलका चौधरी	31
• कवितायें	शुभदा पांडेय एवं मनोहर लाल बाथम	33
• Understanding the Relationship between...	Prof. S. P. Ruhela	34
• Applicability of Psychological Testing	Dr. (Mrs.) S. P. Goel	35
• Contributions of Maulana Azad in Edu.....	Dr. Saroj Yadav & Ms. Sangeeta Chauhan	36
• Eco-Awareness for Personal Sustainability	Dr. (Mrs.) Indira Sharma & Meeta Verma	37
• The Roaring inside Her : (Re) Thinking.....	Dr. Parveen Kaur Khanna & Dr. Arvind Khanna	38
• Behavioural Disorder : Types and Treatment	Dr. Gita Gulati & Dr. Raina Tiwari	40
• Loneliness in Transition Period :	Dr. Rituja Kaur	42
• Cause of Water Pollution	Rajshree	44
• DLF Indian Premier League (IPL) Series Cricket		46
• Conferences		47

शिक्षामित्र-त्रैमासिक में समस्त प्रकाशित सामग्री का कॉपीराइट पत्रिका का होगा तथा इसमें प्रकाशित सभी साहित्य के तथ्यों तथा विचारों की प्रस्तुति की जिम्मेदारी लेखक या रचनाकार की होगी इसके लिये सम्पादक का कोई दायित्व नहीं है।

विवाद की स्थिति में आगरा न्यायालय मान्य होगा।

सम्पादक : विवेक भार्गव

स्वामी, प्रकाशक, मुद्रक एवं सम्पादक -
विवेक भार्गव, 4/230, कचहरी घाट,
आगरा-282 004 के लिये राष्ट्रभाषा
ऑफसेट प्रेस, 26/471, बल्का बस्ती,
राजामंडी, आगरा-282 002 द्वारा मुद्रित।

Cause of Water Pollution

Rajshree

In INDIA many causes of pollution, including sewage, manure, and chemical fertilizers, contain "nutrients" such as nitrates and phosphates. Deposition of atmospheric nitrogen (from nitrogen oxides) also causes nutrient-type water pollution. In excess levels, nutrients over-stimulate the growth of aquatic plants and algae. Excessive growth of these types of organisms clogs our waterways and blocks light to deeper waters while the organisms are alive; when the organisms die, they use up dissolved oxygen as they decompose, causing oxygen-poor waters that support only diminished amounts of marine life. Such areas are commonly called dead zones. Nutrient pollution is a particular problem in estuaries and deltas, where the runoff that was aggregated by watersheds is finally dumped at the mouths of major rivers.

Ground water pollution occurs when chemicals, debris, garbage, oil or other harmful contaminants enter the ground water supply over time. Ground water is often a resource for our drinking water. If it isn't treated properly, those harmful elements can cause serious health issues for human beings and domestic animals.

Oil spills do cause major water pollution and problems for wildlife, fishermen, and coastal businesses. But the problem of oil polluting water goes far beyond catastrophic oil spills. Land-based petroleum pollution is carried into waterways by rainwater runoff. This includes drips of oil, fuel, and fluid from cars and trucks; dribbles of gasoline spilled onto the ground at the filling station; and drips from industrial machinery. These sources and more combine to provide a continual feed of petroleum pollution to all of the world's waters, imparting an amount of oil to the oceans *every year* that is more than 5 times greater than the spill. Shipping is one of these non-spill sources of oil pollution in water : Discharge of oily wastes and oil-contaminated ballast water and wash water are all significant sources of marine pollution, and

drips from ship and boat motors add their share. Drilling and extraction operations for oil and gas can also contaminate coastal waters and groundwater. As for gasoline and gas additives, leaking storage tanks are a big problem. The US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) estimates that about 100,000 gasoline storage tanks are leaking chemicals into groundwater. In Santa Monica, California, wells supplying half the city's water have been closed because of dangerously high levels of the gasoline additive MTBE.

Mining causes water pollution in a number of ways :

- The mining process exposes heavy metals and sulfur compounds that were previously locked away in the earth. Rainwater leaches these compounds out of the exposed earth, resulting in "acid mine drainage" and heavy metal pollution that can continue long after the mining operations have ceased.
- Similarly, the action of rainwater on piles of mining waste (tailings) transfers pollution to freshwater supplies.
- In the case of gold mining, cyanide is intentionally poured on piles of mined rock (a leach heap) to chemically extract the gold from the ore. Some of the cyanide ultimately finds its way into nearby water.
- Huge pools of mining waste "slurry" are often stored behind containment dams. If a dam leaks or bursts, water pollution is guaranteed.

Perhaps the worst offense in the category of mining vs. water pollution causes: Mining companies in developing countries sometimes dump mining waste directly into rivers or other bodies of water as a method of disposal.

When forests are "clear cut," the root systems that previously held soil in place die and sediment is free to run off into nearby streams, rivers, and lakes. Thus, not only does clear cutting have serious effects on plant and animal

biodiversity in the forest, the increased amount of sediment running off the land into nearby bodies of water seriously affects fish and other aquatic life. Poor farming practices that leave soil exposed to the elements also contribute to sediment pollution in water. Plastics and other plastic-like substances (such as nylon from fishing nets and lines) can entangle fish, sea turtles, and marine mammals, causing pain, injury, and even death. Plastic that has broken down into micro-particles is now being ingested by tiny marine organisms and is moving up the marine food chain. Sea creatures that are killed by plastic readily decompose. The plastic does not—it remains in the ecosystem to kill again and again.

Whenever we use personal-care products and household cleaning products—whether they be laundry detergent, bleach, or fabric softener; window cleaner, dusting spray, or stain remover; hair dye, shampoo, conditioner, or Rogaine; cologne or perfume; toothpaste or mouthwash; antibacterial soap or hand lotion—we should realize that almost all of it goes down the drain when we do laundry, wash our hands, brush our teeth, bathe, or do any of the other myriad things that incidentally use household water. Similarly, when we take medications, we eventually excrete the drugs in altered or unaltered form, sending the compounds into the waterways. Studies have shown that up to 90% of your original prescription passes out of you unaltered. Animal farming operations that use growth hormones and antibiotics also send large quantities of these chemicals into our waters. Unfortunately, most wastewater treatment facilities are not equipped to filter out personal care products, household products, and pharmaceuticals, and a large portion of the chemicals passes right into the local waterway that accepts the treatment plant's supposedly clean effluent.

Study of the effects of these chemicals getting into the water is just beginning, but examples of problems are now popping up regularly:

- Scientists are finding fragrance molecules inside fish tissues.
- Ingredients from birth control pills are thought to be causing gender-bending hormonal effects in frogs and fish.
- The chemical nonylphenol, a remnant of detergent, is known to disrupt fish reproduction and growth.

In developing countries an estimated 90% of wastewater is discharged directly into rivers and streams without treatment. Even in modern countries, untreated sewage, poorly treated sewage, or overflow from under-capacity sewage treatment facilities can send disease-bearing water into rivers and oceans.

Major Effects of Water Pollution

The effects of water pollution are numerous (as seen above). Some water pollution effects are recognized immediately. Whereas others don't show up for months or years. Additional effects of water pollution include:

1. **The food chain is damaged**—When toxins are in the water, the toxins travel from the water the animals drink to humans when the animals' meat is eaten.
2. **Diseases can spread via polluted water**—Infectious diseases such as typhoid and cholera can be contracted from drinking contaminated water. This is called microbial water pollution. The human heart and kidneys can be adversely affected if polluted water is consumed regularly. Other health problems associated with polluted water are poor blood circulation, skin lesions, vomiting, and damage to the nervous system. In fact, the effects of water pollution are said to be the leading cause of death for humans across the globe.
3. **Acid rain** contains sulfate particles, which can harm fish or plant life in lakes and rivers.
4. **Pollutants in the water will alter the overall chemistry of the water**, causing changes in acidity, temperature and conductivity. These factors all have an affect on the marine life.
5. **Marine food sources are contaminated** or eliminated by water pollution.
6. **Altered water temperatures (due to human actions) can kill the marine life** and affect the delicate ecological balance in bodies of water, especially lakes and rivers.

Water pollution effects have a huge impact on our environment and health. The delicate balance between nature and humans can be protected, but it will take efforts on all fronts to prevent and eliminate water pollution locally and globally.

